

Measurement of Cation in Na^+ , Ca^{++} , Cu^{++} , and Fe^{+++} Perchlorate Solutions

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Activities of different mono-, bi-, trivalent cations, in their perchlorate solutions have been measured satisfactorily in the ranges, 0.027*M* to 0.00033*M* for mono-, 0.00081*M* to 0.0001*M* for bi- and 0.00081*M* to 0.00027*M* for trivalent ions respectively.

After having tested the general performance of the different types of membranes¹ as regards their stability, electrical resistance, attainment of equilibrium etc., they are used for measurements with solutions of known ionic activities. These measurements are designed mainly to ascertain the range of ionic activities within which the membrane gives values of e.m.f. in agreement with the Nernst equation. The mean value of e.m.f. within ± 0.2 mv is generally recorded. (Mc-3470XL cation-exchange permselective membrane of Ionac Company is used)*

Measurement of Na^+ ion activity of NaClO_4 solution : Measurements with NaClO_4 solution having strengths varying from 0.027*M* to 0.00033*M* have been performed, in which range the membranes are found to be valid. The mean e.m.f. values with solutions having 3 : 1 ratio in molalities within this range are given in Table 1. All the membranes so tested in this manner give fairly concordant values with the theoretical.

TABLE 1

NaClO ₄ solution	E.m.f. measured in m.v. ± 0.2					
	Me 1	Me 2	Me 3	Me 4	Me 5	Me 6
$\frac{0.027 M}{0.009 M}$	29.0	28.7	27.8	28.3	28.4	28.3
$\frac{0.009 M}{0.003 M}$	28.5	28.2	27.5	28.1	28.2	28.2
$\frac{0.003 M}{0.001 M}$	28.5	28.4	27.3	28.3	28.2	28.3
$\frac{0.001 M}{0.00033M}$	28.6	28.3	27.5	28.3	28.3	28.2

Theoretical value = 28.2 m.v.

Me = Membrane number.

1. C. E. Marshall, "Physical Chemistry and Mineralogy of Soils", Vol. I, John Wiley and Sons, New York.

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TABLE 2

Ca(ClO ₄) ₂ Solution	E.m.f. measured in m.v. ± 0.2					
	Me 1	Me 2	Me 3	Me 4	Me 5	Me 6
$\frac{0.0081M}{0.0027M}$	14.0	14.1	14.4	13.9	14.0	—
$\frac{0.0027M}{0.0009M}$	14.1	14.1	14.3	14.0	14.0	14.0
$\frac{0.0009M}{0.0003M}$	14.2	14.1	14.3	14.0	14.2	—
$\frac{0.0003M}{0.0001M}$	14.2	14.0	14.2	14.1	14.2	—

Theoretical value = 14.1 m.v.

Me = Membrane number.

TABLE 3

Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ Solution	E.m.f. measured in m.v. ± 0.2				
	Me 1	Me 2	Me 3	Me 4	Me 5
$\frac{0.0009M}{0.0003M}$	14.0	14.0	14.4	14.4	14.0
$\frac{0.0003M}{0.0001M}$	14.1	14.1	14.3	14.1	14.0

Theoretical value = 14.1 M.V.

Me = Membrane number.

TABLE 4

Fe(ClO ₄) ₃ Solution pH = 2.9	E.m.f. measured in m.v. ± 0.2			
	Me 1	Me 2	Me 3	Me 4
$\frac{0.00081M}{0.00027M}$	9.2	9.6	9.4	9.3
$\frac{0.00027M}{0.00009M}$	9.3	9.5	9.2	9.3

Theoretical value = 9.4 m.v.

Me = Membrane number.

Perchlorates are assumed to be completely dissociated in the dilute ranges used by us so that the difference between activity and molarity is negligible.

In spite of the insolubility of KClO₄, the saturated calomel electrodes having KCl—agar tip performed satisfactorily.

Measurement of Bivalent Ion Activities in Perchlorate solutions: One of the main difficulties of measurements with bivalent metal perchlorates is that the pure anhydrous

compounds are not easily available. Therefore they have to be prepared from other compounds by treatment with HClO_4 .

Since the membranes are sensitive to H^+ ions, the $p\text{H}$ of the solutions is to be maintained as far as possible near neutrality.

Measurement of Ca^{++} ion activity: Measurements with $\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ solution have been performed in the range $0.0081M$ to $0.0001M$ over which the membranes were found to be valid.

Measurement of Cu^{++} ions activity: The range of validity of membranes for Cu^{++} perchlorate is between $0.0009M$ to $0.0001M$. More concentrated solutions than the highest in the range could not be prepared owing to limited solubility of copper perchlorate.

Measurement of Trivalent Ion activity: Attempts to measure the ionic activity of trivalent cations with membranes are not very successful and are beset with difficulties. There are at least two reasons². Firstly, the trivalent cations are likely to be adsorbed by the membranes rendering them positively charged so that the membrane would become anion sensitive; secondly, the dissociation of the trivalent ions from the surface would be so small that the effective charge density "A" will decrease considerably. In that circumstances, the concentration at which the Nernst equation is valid would be so low that considerable hydrolysis would set in, disturbing the ionic equilibrium.

Measurement of Fe^{+++} ion activity: $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ undergoes hydrolysis very rapidly causing the asymmetry in the membranes and also changing the activities of the solutions. The hydrolysis can be stopped by keeping the acid concentration of the solutions high. But it is not always possible to maintain exactly equal H^+ ion concentration between two electrolytic solutions used and the difference of H^+ ion concentration causes deviation from the theoretical values.

Besides, high acidity of the solutions used sometimes causes the cracking and leakage in the membranes. To avoid these difficulties the following steps are followed.

1. Always fresh solutions are taken.
2. One stock acid solution is prepared and that solution instead of water is used for preparing different $\text{Fe}(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ solutions.
3. Before potential measurement, $p\text{H}$ values of the solutions are measured with a "Cambridge $p\text{H}$ Meter" and solutions having the same $p\text{H}$ are taken.
4. To stop hydrolysis partly the membranes are never washed with water. Dilute solutions of the same ion are used for the experiment and ultimately the final solution is used for washing.

After several attempts measurements of Fe^{+3} ion activities in the limited concentration range $0.00081M$ to $0.00009M$ were possible.